

Historical Perspective Of Solo Piano Music Of Thai Composers

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Abstract

Commercially published compositions in numerical notation, and even in western notation, may be purchased at stores in Bangkok. One professional musician, now a university professor, showed me a cabinet full of such publications in his home, but claimed that none of them were accurate. I imagined that the printers had erred, but my informant explained that in the past when publishers approached teachers for songs, the latter were extremely reluctant to make public their special knowledge. Teachers would agree to sell a song, yet they purposely put in "mistakes," saving the "real" version for their own students. In this way the traditional bond of teacher and student—always articulated by the transmission of guarded knowledge—remained intact. At the same time bonds between teachers and students who might purchase and use the published music were strengthened as well: it was common knowledge that the printed music was inaccurate, so students were forced to go to their own teachers who could pick out the errors and teach a recognized version.

This study illustrates well the generational conflict between an older teacher, prejudiced and skeptical towards notation, and a young student acculturated to Western music who is still able to become proficient in Thai music. Yet it seems that very few if any musicians, even those who consider themselves most traditional, completely avoid notation now.

Introduction

The neglect of other nations of the Far East, particularly those of Southeast Asia, has created a gap in the literature on the cross-cultural interplay in compositions that blend Western and Far Eastern elements in art music. With Thailand in particular, there is no single work on the musical fusion of Thai and Western elements available. Accessible studies related to Thai music focus on Thai music alone, with the most cited being David Morton's *The Traditional Music of Thailand* (1976), which covers the basic groundwork of Thai music from its history, musical elements, instruments, and compositional techniques. Another less-mentioned reliable source is Pamela A. Myers-Moro's *Thai Music and Musicians in Contemporary Bangkok* (1993).

Humans have impressive abilities to recognize structure and patterns in the world, in multiple modalities and many domains. For example, we can recognize familiar voices on the phone and identify objects at unusual sizes and angles. Music, in particular, is a good domain in which to study pattern recognition because of its many patterns at many levels of complexity and abstraction, which allow research into auditory perception across the spectrum from basic processing to high-level real-world tasks. The simplest patterns in music are specific note durations and pitches. Themes are more complex patterns, but even untrained listeners can recognize a theme at its restatement in a piece they have not heard before (Java, Kaminska, & Gardiner, 1995). The composers' styles are perhaps the most abstract and complex patterns that humans can detect in music because these patterns transcend individual pieces or works. Research on perceptual learning and research specifically on composer style contributes insights into our ability to recognize composer styles, which are abstract auditory patterns.

Perceptual learning (PL) refers to improvements in the pickup of information as a function of experience (Gibson, 1969). In particular, PL has been shown to accelerate the development of expert pattern recognition, contributing to the development of expertise. PL is well-established in both vision (Sagi, 2010) and audition (Sabin, Eddins, & Wright, 2012). Much work in both modalities has focused on expertise in low-level discriminations. For example, many studies have demonstrated PL in studies of pitch duration (e.g., Karmarkar & Buonomano, 2003) or orientated visual gratings (e.g., Song, Peng, Lu, Liu, & Li, 2007). However, perceptual learning also supports the extraction of relations in complex domains. In the vision, recent research suggests that PL can be systematically accelerated in aviation (Kellman & Kaiser, 1994), medicine (Thai, Krasne, & Kellman, 2015), mathematics (e.g., Kellman & Massey, 2013; Kellman, Massey, & Son, 2010; Landy & Goldstone, 2007), and other complex domains. Perceptual and adaptive learning modules (PALMs) accomplish this acceleration by using brief, interactive classification trials (e.g., Mettler & Kellman, 2014; Mettler, Massey, & Kellman, 2011). PALMs have only been created for visual stimuli thus far, which do not share the temporal

nature of auditory stimuli. Can principles enhancing visual learning be extended to auditory stimuli, such as music?

Psychologists studying musical style perception have focused primarily on documenting human sensitivity to period styles (e.g., Hasenpus, Martindale & Birnbaum, 1983), developing hundreds of machine learning programs that simulate this impressive human ability (e.g., Widmer, 2005). However, while our human ability to recognize patterns in period styles has been well-documented, psychologists have done very little empirical work on whether humans have a similar sensitivity to composer styles, a topic that musicologists have long been interested in and discussed. Tyler (1946) played the three movements of a Mozart sonata and selected and played three movements each of trios by Beethoven and Schubert to students in a music appreciation course and found that students could distinguish between the composers better than chance. However, she did not control musical form (e.g., sonata or ballad), nor did she study learning. Crump (2002) chose J. S. Bach and Mozart because the composers were "stylistically distinct" and then only used the Goldberg variations for Bach and Minuets for Mozart. Participants and a machine learning algorithm successfully learned to distinguish these composers, but confounding musical form with composer limits the generalizability of these results. Due to the limitations of these studies, the empirical proof of composer style and the learnability of composer style is uncertain.

Apart from the literature on musical exoticism and Thai music, research on younger generations of East and Southeast Asian composers likewise overlook the synthesis of Thai and Western elements. Numerous twentieth- and twenty-first-century Asian composers from various countries have been studied, leaving out Thai composers who practice similar compositional processes. Among these Asian contemporary composers, the Japanese Toru Takemitsu (1930- 1996) 's fusion is probably the most scrutinized, including in Hwee Been Koh's dissertation "East and West: The Aesthetics and Musical Time of Toru Takemitsu" (1998) and Peter Burt's *The Music of Toru Takemitsu* (2001), as well as Takemitsu's perspective on the topic in *Confronting Silences* (1995), which includes a selection of his writings.

Thai music for piano solo arranged by Sumitra Sucharitkul and Col. Choochart Pitaksakorn was notated according to the interpretation of Professor Dr. Natchar Pancharoen, the only person who learned Thai music by rote on the piano with the two masters. The main objectives of notating all pieces of piano solo music into the standard score are to promote Thai music to the public. The most important musical element is the use of ornaments which are characteristic in Thai music. The major difference between Tiew Hwan (slow variation) and Tiew Keb (fast variation) is the movement of the melody. In slow variations, the melody imitates the style of Thai singing, which is highly ornamented, while in fast variations, the melody moves steadily with more notes and is less ornamented.

However, specific performance details, such as articulations, fingering, and dynamics, have not been written in the notation. The pianists have some room for interpretation on their own. "Solo" in Thai classical music is created for playing by one instrument and used for "showing off" the player's skills on that certain instrument. Solo for the Thai piano music follows the authentic Thai classical music approaches. The harmony used is western standard, arranged with advanced classical piano techniques. Every piece contains specific characters of a variety of Thai classical instruments mixed with piano techniques. Most Thai pieces arranged for the piano are in a western style which does not strictly comply with Thai classical notation. As for the Thai music solo, there are only two musician composers – Khru Sumitra Sucharitkul and Col.Choochart Pitaksakorn - who arranged the music with the traditional Thai style.

This thesis is a first step toward the literature of cross-cultural synthesis between Thai and Western elements in Western art music, presenting Narong Prangcharoen (1973) and his orchestral works as a case study. Prangcharoen has established himself as a leading twenty-first-century composer, especially after receiving a Fellowship from the John Simon Guggenheim Memorial Foundation and the Barlow Prize in 2013. This paper aims to survey the history and forms of written notation as musicians in the Thai classical tradition have tied it. With an emphasis upon the functions and implications of notation, while the topic is of significance in its own right, it also touches upon broader issues such as acculturation, the social organization of performing artists, and the interface between oral and written tradition. Most significantly, we must ask to what extent the use of notation signifies changing values and represents altered contexts of music learning in Thailand.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to assess the historical perspective of solo piano music of Thai composers.

Specifically, the following questions were answered.

1. What are the background information about famous Thai composers and their music?
2. What are the historical background to and stylistic discussion of all movements of their music?
3. What are the in-depth analyses of the first movement of their music?
4. What are the Thai musical influences to society?

Significance of the Study

In order to glimpse the implications of notation on Thai music-making, it is necessary to examine how notation is used. Here we can see the adoption of the technology of written music within a tradition of musical transmission which is still fundamentally oral, with music passed from teacher to student. While over the past several decades published notation of music has been available for students and amateurs, by far the most common use of notation now is by teachers who notate, by hand, during lessons with students. The "giving" of a composition from teacher to student remains.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

The Thai term for notation tells much of the origin of the idea of writing down music: the English word "note," pronounced *noot*, is used, sometimes as *noot phleeng thay*, the latter words meaning "Thai song," specifically Thai classical music. The first known notation of Thai music-by anyone, foreigner or Thai-was that of Simon de La Loubere in the 17th century (Figure 1). La Loubere was a traveler who compiled an astonishingly encyclopedic account of Siamese life and customs; his notated version of a Thai melody is of such symbolic significance that it became one of the sources for the melody of the contemporary Royal Anthem. To my knowledge it was a long time after La Loubere's visit, however, before Thai music was again notated, this time for military bands with Western instruments, playing Thai melodies, in the second half of the 19th century (I do not know whether it was Thai or foreigners who wrote down the melodies; it was most likely Thai performing them~ however, for various accounts testify to the performance of Western musical ensembles with Thai personnel during that period). What loom large, however, in the history of Thai notation as told by my informants and in Thai-authored sources, are the 20th-century efforts to use Western notation to record and preserve Thai music, as well as indigenous systems designed solely for use by Thai. In a short English-language article, Phra Chen Duriyanga-renowned for fostering the Thai performance of Western classical music in this century-reminds about the first (and only major) attempt to preserve Thai music with Western notation, recalling that Prince Damrong Rajanubhab, through Thailand's Royal Institute, spearheaded the effort in 1930 (or, approximately 1930, for sources vary)³. A committee was formed of Thai who could read and write Western notation-largely members of Phra Chen's Western orchestra-and their task was to write down as much music as possible. Phra Chen himself was not a performer of Thai music at all, and studied the instruments only enough to carry out the notation.

An informant explained that recordings of Thai music were also made at the time, intended for preservation, but these were lost during World War II bombing while awaiting manufacture in Germany. The result of these efforts is a collection of some four hundred compositions, either in score form for ensemble or simply "middle versions" [*thaang klaang klaang*] of melodies which might be taught to a beginning student but which are realized, rather than actually played, in performance by accomplished musicians (Figure 2). Most of the notated compositions are familiar works from the *seephaa mahoorii* or "entertainment" branch of repertoire, those songs which are most likely to be taught to youngsters and to amateur musicians (that is, not theater music and the ritually-significant *naa phaata*).

These manuscripts formed the basis of David Morton's scholarly studies of Thai music, and microfilm copies are stored in the archives of the University of California at Los Angeles's Institute of Ethnomusicology. Some of the notations have been published by Thailand's Department of Fine Arts. Furthermore, the National Library stores some of the old manuscripts of military band arrangements, and still other notations are housed at the Musical Arts Center of the Bangkok Bank. It appears that the invention of indigenous notation occurred well after the earliest efforts by foreigners to write down Thai music, yet somewhat before Phra Chen's effort to

utilize Western notation for preservation. One source dates the development of specifically-Thai notation at 1913. I have heard of no indication that Thai-style notation existed in the 19th century or earlier.

The use of Western and Thai systems of notation has always contrasted greatly. If the Western-style notation of Thai music was intended as preservation, there its function stopped: today, "scholars, not musicians," as one informant put it, are the only people to utilize any of these manuscripts. They are not used for performance or for teaching. Western notation of songs does appear in some of the Thai-authored texts on music. One musician joked that Western notation is too complicated, and compared its appearance to a kind of Thai plant which has curly leaves and stems. In contrast, the Thai systems are clear, easy to read, can be learned even by a beginner in a matter of minutes, and are superbly appropriate for the purposes they generally serve: they impart just enough information (the outline of the main melody) to help a beginning student learn, to enable an amateur player to have fun, or to serve as a mnemonic device for advanced or even professional musicians. Written sources and oral accounts cite Luang Pradit Phayrau as the first musician to create a system for notating Thai music, although others developed similar systems soon thereafter. His daughter, Khunying Chin Silpabanleng, cites precisely the use of notation as both a mnemonic and teaching aid: "In those days (1913) music study was done by memory. Those who taught and those who studied wasted a lot of time. My father had to teach music over and over. Then he thought of signs to help improve the memory." Luang Pradit's system employs numerals 1 through 9 for pitches on the *sau duang*, *sau uu* (the two-stringed fiddles), and *khluu* (flute), and numerals 1 through 12 for *cakhee* (zither).

Background information about famous Thai composers and their music

The tradition of oversea education produced the individual many consider Thailand's first composer in the Western mold, HRH Prince Paribatra (1881-1944), one of King Rama V's sons. Similar to other royal families, Prince Paribatra learned Thai instruments and singing as a child in the royal court before departing for England in 1894 to further his education. Two years later, he pursued a military education in Germany. Although music was his passion, the prince could not follow the path to a professional music career, but continued to leisurely study piano and conducting and attend musical performances during his time in Europe. Upon his return to Thailand in 1903, Rama V appointed him Commander-in-Chief of the Royal Thai Army, and a year later of the Royal Thai Navy, a subsection of the Ministry of Defense at that time. With his interest in Western music, which conformed to Rama V's modernization policy, the Prince developed the Thai navy band by teaching a course called "Brass Instrument Applications" in 1906 at the Navy Department and occasionally directing the band. Besides his Western musical activities, the Prince also resumed his interest in Thai music by forming a Thai musical ensemble called *Wong Phin Wang Phat Bang Khun Phrom* at his court, *Bang Khun Phrom* palace.

Most importantly, Prince Paribatra became the first Thai to compose and arrange music for the military band in the Western style with written musical notation. His works can be divided in three categories: 1) newly-composed works, 2) arrangements of Thai music in a Western style, and 3) arrangements of Thai music in a Thai style. His newly-composed works include a march, a polka, and three waltzes in the style of nineteenth-century Western military band music. For his arrangements in a Western style, Prince Paribatra adopted the fusion process of eighteenth- and nineteenth-century Western musical exoticism, something to which he might have been exposed during his stay in Europe. The process is distinctive for its application of a pre-existing Eastern tune or a newly composed pentatonic melody that rests above Western-style harmonization. Following this scheme, Prince Paribatra regularly borrowed a Thai melody and transformed it for his Western military band by adding harmonization and orchestration. The most prominent works in this category are two songs of honor, *Maharok* and *Mahachai*, which have been used in ceremonial inaugurations to the present day. The last category of Prince Paribatra's works, the arrangements of Thai music in Thai style, reflects the Prince's expertise in Thai music. Influenced perhaps by the cross-cultural process that appeared in the earlier Thai military band's repertoire of Thai songs, the Prince did not Westernize Thai music, rather he "Thai-ized" a Western military band by assigning them to play Thai music, following the original practices of melody, rhythmic structure, and polyphonic stratification. In other words, he replaced Thai *pi-phat* instruments with Western winds. Two Thai percussion instruments, *ching* (a pair of small cymbals) and *taphon* (drum), govern the rhythmic section while Western wind instruments form two stratified polyphonic lines of melody and variations of the main melody. Bassoon, saxophone, trombone, and euphonium replace *khong-wong-yai* (large horizontal melodic gongs) for the main melody. These instruments, together with trumpet and tuba, sometimes play the variations that originally appeared on *khong-wong-lek* (small horizontal melodic gongs) or *ranat-thum* (lower-pitched wooden xylophone). *Piccolo*, flute, clarinet, and oboe are responsible for the *ranat-ek* (higher-pitched wooden xylophone) part, which presents either the melody or its variations.

Apart from the instrumental music sphere, the appearance of cross-cultural fusion also increased in the theatrical domain. *Peng Penkun* (*Chao Phraya Mahinthornsakthamrong*) created *La-khon Phan Thang* ("hybrid drama") during Rama IV's reign but it remained in the style of traditional Thai drama. In 1857, *Penkun*, as *Chargé d' Affaires*, joined Rama IV's diplomatic corps in presenting a royal message to Queen Victoria of the United Kingdom. Influenced by Western plays and operas experienced during the sojourn, *Penkun* transformed

his Phan Thang drama from a single-gender cast to one with male and female actors according to the gender of the characters. He also exploited plots, dancing, costumes, and musical styles and instruments of foreign nations. The Western influence also appeared in scenic effects of Penkun's newly built Prince Theatre, the first theatre in Thailand that cost admission. After the death of Penkun, his son Boosra took over the theatre and changed the name of the drama to La-khon Boosra Mahin.

Phan Thang drama opened a way to two short-lived Western-influenced Thai dramas, La-khon Duek Dam Ban and tableaux vivants. Existed during 1899-1909, Duek Dam Ban drama derived from the so-called "Concert"—an adaptation of Thai music for a two-part male and female chorus and Wong Pi-phat—which M.R.L Larn Kunchorn (Chao Phraya Thewet

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system employs numerals 1 through 9 for pitches on the sau duang, sau uu (the two-stringed fiddles), and khloy (flute), and numerals 1 through 12 for cakhee (zither).

Originally, Luang Pradit's system utilized patterns of short vertical and horizontal lines to indicate rhythm and repetition of notes. Later the system was revised to make rhythm easier to read. Numerals were set off in groups to represent "measures" (similar to those in Western music) indicating metric stress, and simple rhythmic events - outside of straight one - note per one-beat movement, which is what the system notates most easily- could be shown by short curved lines or open spaces. A variation of this system indicates pitches in a higher octave by dots over numerals, reinforcing the fact that pitch 1 is still pitch 1 even when an octave higher: Today the most commonly-used modification of Luang Pradit's system among players of stringed instruments uses two ruled lines, each line representing a string, and numerals representing the fingers to be placed on each string. String players possibly use notation more frequently than other musicians because stringed instruments are those more frequently played by amateurs-as we'll get to below. Yet another system of notation uses letters based upon Western solmization (do, re, mi, etc.). This system is currently used in school classrooms when teaching khloy (flute). It is important to remember that here, as in the other Thai notation systems and throughout Thai musical theory, there is what Western musicians call a "non-movable do." That is, the letter dau (~) or pitch #1 always remains the same, regardless of its function within a piece of music, regardless of what mode or pitch level the piece occurs in. Furthermore, there is a consistent alteration in all Western notations of Thai music which could cause confusion to Westerners. The Western "do" (Thai dau), always written in Thailand as note C, sounds "re" (Western note D), and all other pitches are correspondingly one note "off." Those who write down Thai music have generally found it easier to consistently use C Major, which has no sharps and flats, than the more accurate-according to the conventional Western relationship of notation to actual pitch-D Major.

The concern for loss of repertoire may also indicate an increase in the Thai (or at least Thai musician's and scholar's) consciousness of changes which occur through time. Undoubtedly repertoire of previous eras had been lost through the vagaries of oral tradition, as a regular part of history which musicians either did not know about or did not care to comment upon. Yet as Phra Chen Duriyanga pointed out, concern over the loss of Thai music in the present era was stimulated when Prince Damrong reviewed a list of the names of Siamese songs and it was discovered that " more than 50 per cent of the melodies had already been lost forever. " (Becker quotes similar sentiments from Javanese sources).⁶ This is a modern concern, perhaps related to the 19th century romantic views which brought about the studies of folklore and anthropology, among other fields (tied so closely to feelings of nationalism, which were also growing in Siam at the time of musical notation). Both Phra Chen and Prince Damrong, who had Western educations, were surely aware of such notions. (Phra Chen, who was originally named Peter Feit, had an American father and a German education; Prince Damrong, a half-brother of King Rama V, was a leading scholar of his time and is known as the "father of Thai history.")

Because foreign contact with Siam, attempts by foreigners to notate Siamese music, and the arrangement of Siamese music for Western brass band all occurred significantly before the major effort at preservation in the 1930s, one wonders why transcribing did not occur earlier, were it not for the force of acculturated ideas regarding change. Furthermore, by the first decades of the 20th century scholars and musicians had had opportunity to see that foreign forms of entertainment-seen by many as invasive and debilitating-were becoming very popular. Since the late 19th century, Siamese theater had become "reformed" by incorporating certain Western characteristics? By 1932 films and distinctive film-inspired songs were being produced in Thailand, and foreign films had been imported for some time before that.⁸ The days of abundant royal and noble support for Thai music ended in 1925 with the death of King Rama VI, and after the coup d'etat of 1932 musicians were fully incorporated into the government bureaucracy, altering the traditional context in which students studied with master musicians.

Those who would seek to preserve Thai music may have had very real concerns about its future, even though the 1930s notation effort began before the era of Japanese occupation and of Prime Minister Phibul Songkhraam, whose social change policies-which included government licensing and censoring of performers-gave many musicians even more cause to worry about the demise of their art. The impetus behind invention of Thai systems of notation is more difficult to pinpoint. As Khunying Chin pointed out, such notation saved time for teachers and aided memory, yet why would such concerns not have inspired earlier musicians to create a recording system? Two possible explanations both point, again, to cultural changes due to contact with the West and the increasingly cosmopolitan nature of Thai life. First, the very notion-of writing down music in a manner which was of use to teachers and students may have been borrowed from the West. In this light, musical notation may be seen as part of the broader phenomenon of increasing literacy in Thailand.

The implementation of a national system of public schools, and the idea that all Thai citizens could become literate, developed in the first decades of the 20th century, coinciding with the advent of musical notation. Second, the notions that time can be wasted or saved, that memory needs to be helped (because if it's not, then one loses time) are similarly not indigenous. The brilliance of the Thai solution-from the perspective of Thai music as we know it-was to create systems of notation which could not be used uniformly throughout the

entire repertoire (because they would have meant significant and inevitable changes in the nature of the music—perhaps along the lines Judith Becker⁹ suggests), which did not divorce the student from the teacher, and which thus kept intact many aspects of the traditional social organization of musicians.

Khru Sumitra Sucharitkul (1907-1984) is the model for Thai piano solos. She was a court pianist in the era of King Rama VI. She also played the piano together with Thai traditional string ensembles. Khru Sumitra was taught by many Thai classical music teachers. She included western techniques in her music but still preserved the Thai classical tunes with the use of fundamental harmony. Many times, there were melodies played in an octave apart with no harmony. Only 3 pieces were notated which are Tab Lao Charoen Sri, Nok Khamin Sam Chan and Phaya Soke (Natchar Phancharoen, 2008:16-17).

The other musician composers, Col. Choochart Pitaksakorn (1934-) is a violinist and conductor. He is honoured as the National Artist in Performing Arts (western music) in 2010. He arranged a great number of Thai classical pieces for western band. Choochart's solo uses advanced harmony with insertion of counterpoint. The outstanding character is the use of chromatic notes in his harmonic arrangement while the melodies are decorated with Thai classical music elements. Although Col. Choochart is known for his skills in playing the violin or the viola, he is also a skillful classical pianist. So his Thai piano solo arrangement is full of advanced classical piano techniques. Col. Choochart arranged altogether 7 Thai piano solo pieces: Somsongsaeng (tao) , Sai Yoke Sam Chan, Lao Pan, Fon Ngiew, Nok Khamin Sam Chan, Phaya Soke Sam Chan and Saratee Sam Chan. Both Khru Sumitra and Col. Choochart transferred his music by demonstration, teaching by words and by rote, which are the methods of teaching Thai classical music. Most works of Khru Sumitra were performed in court while Col. Choochart's works were performed in public during 1971-1983. The only person to whom his music was transferred is Dr. Natchar Phancharoen. Up to present, these musical pieces have never been notated. The first piano solo notation was made by Dr. Natchar who wanted to preserve and spread this piano works which are regarded as a Thai piano literature. She then asked the author to invent the method for Thai classical piano solo notation.

The notation for Thai piano solo is not only comply with the western standard but also includes the invention of methods used for notating the techniques played by variety of Thai instruments. So it is crucial to understand the composer's intention to convey elements of certain Thai classical instruments and bring it to the score to be playable by the piano. The main propose of the notation is to make it a universal communication for pianists or other western musicians to understand and play the music, regardless of his or his knowledge of Thai music. Therefore, the process of notation includes many factors. In terms of the theory, the use of time signature and key signature has to be planned. The melodic and rhythmic patterns have to be set up. The harmonic arrangement has to enhance the melodies. The essential factor is the use of ornaments which make the piano convey Thainess and make it possible to notate the piano techniques. In the process of notation, there is another crucial factor at the beginning of the notation process that is the knowledge and understanding of fundamental Thai music which will help to path the way to the appropriate and correct notation.

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Dr. Natchar's performance and interpretation which is unique is used. The method is listening and jotting both directly and from recording. Only Col. Choochart's Phaya Soke Sam Chan is notated by original notated score. Khru Sumitra's Nok Khamin Sam Chan and Praya Soke Sam Chan notation are taken from her recording. After that, notate from Dr. Natchar's interpretation and arrangement to complete the playing techniques and harmony but still keep Khru Sumitra's. The melodic notation must be thorough and needs the understanding of the Thai thematic melody. The analysis of the melodic structure has to be done: find out that each element comes from the improvisation of which melody. In the Tiew Hwan that mainly uses Euan, many times, there is an extension of main notes which can be regarded as rubato in western music. For performing, although it has to be played from reading the notation, the performer has to be capable of inserting their ways of techniques. But this may be different from the original arrangement. So in notating, the methods of notation all playing techniques have to be invented to notate as the arrangement requires.

In order to glimpse the implications of notation on Thai music-making, it is necessary to examine how notation is used. Here we can see the adoption of the technology of written music within a tradition of musical transmission which is still fundamentally oral, with music passed from teacher to student. While over the past several decades published notation of music has been available for students and amateurs, by far the most common use of notation now is by teachers who notate, by hand, during lessons with students. The "giving" of a composition from teacher to student remains.

The double-ruled system of notation for stringed instruments, and the single-line numerical systems for other instruments, makes convenient use of lined writing paper which one can buy easily and inexpensively in Bangkok. Amateur musicians buy large empty notebooks, the pages to be filled eventually with notated songs, copied out either in the student's own hand or written in by a teacher. The sau duang teacher, who regularly used notation when teaching adult amateur musicians, wrote at least one new song in my notebook each week; the time spent writing in the notebook accounted for the bulk of my one-hour lesson each week. Commercially published compositions in numerical notation, and even in western notation, may be purchased at stores in Bangkok. One professional musician, now a university professor, showed me a cabinet full of such publications in his home, but claimed that none of them were accurate. They imagined that the printers had erred, but my informant explained that in the past when publishers approached teachers for songs, the latter were extremely reluctant to make public their special knowledge.

Teachers would agree to sell a song, yet they purposely put in "mistakes," saving the "real" version for their own students. In this way the traditional bond of teacher and student—always articulated by the transmission of guarded knowledge—remained intact. At the same time bonds between teachers and students who might purchase and use the published music were strengthened as well: it was common knowledge that the printed music was inaccurate, so students were forced to go to their own teachers who could pick out the errors and teach a recognized version. The informants generally argued that notation was not changing Thai music because only a small portion of the total repertoire could be notated at all. One suggested that amateur players who rely upon notated songs (which most amateurs do) must choose only from the approximately 200 songs which can be written down easily in the Thai systems (amateurs don't use Western notation, which granted can notate more "information"). Entire categories of repertoire, such as the naa phaet, compositions with complex rhythms, those in *cangwa lauy* ("floating rhythm," that is, unmetred), and solos, cannot be notated. My aforementioned sau duang teacher, who regularly taught with the aid of notation, did not attempt to notate at all a virtuosic solo which he taught me, for with its abundant ornaments, special bowing effects, and high register it simply could not be rendered in Thai notation, although someone else gave me what he considered a rather ridiculous published version of the same solo, nearly unrecognizable in its pared-down, notated form.

Even relatively simple songs—the standards of amateur playing and child students—can seldom be played accurately if learned only from notation. Details of rhythm and such things as bowing direction will not be notated but must be learned from the teacher. Any ornamentation or elaboration of the melody, such as might be added to a long sustained note, must be learned from the teacher only. Furthermore, I observed a case in which a teacher incorrectly notated a rhythmically difficult passage; each child in an ensemble of his students learned the passage correctly, however, by drilling over and over with the teacher. This example suggests several things: what the teacher teaches overrides what is notated; the students don't really understand notation that well and simply use it as a mnemonic device, reinforcing what they memorize from their teacher; and, the teacher—who wrote in notation every day—was not skilled enough at writing down music to notate correctly what was, in the broad scheme of things, not a particularly difficult composition. Of course so long as students and amateurs rely upon notation, they do not learn the improvisation—or formulaic rendering—characteristic to their own instrument.

Learning to improvise is the hurdle that sets apart the more advanced students who may go on to become accomplished musicians. I did not encounter any hobbyists who improvised at all. This is one reason why ensembles of amateurs and beginning-level students generally perform melodies in unison, rather than in

the swirling eddys (to paraphrase David Morton) of full-blown renditions by highly-trained performers. Judith Becker argues that in Java, contemporary students who memorize "improvised" versions from notation do not internalize the true system of gamelan performance; as far as I can tell, this is not the case in Thailand, where it appears that some students who begin studying with notation do indeed make the leap to accomplished performance. Thai music teachers will steer a student away from notation as soon as possible if the student is seriously interested in music.

This literature illustrates well the generational conflict between an older teacher, prejudiced and skeptical towards notation, and a young student acculturated to Western music who is still able to become proficient in Thai music. Yet it seems that very few if any musicians, even those who consider themselves most traditional, completely avoid notation now. After having met with my primary informant for several months, during which as a good traditionalist he'd both complained that notation "ruined the spirit" of music and expressed hope that notation will prevent the loss of neglected repertoire, I was surprised one day to see him consult a large notebook similar to those I'd seen amateur musicians use. He was attempting to play a song for me which he'd performed not long before, and because, he explained, the version of the song was from outside his "school," he could not remember it easily. So, he consulted the notebook, in which were written countless songs, in a small, neat hand. He glanced at the problematic passage, then set the notebook flat on the ground in front of his *rpnaat* (xylophone), stealing a quick glance at it now and then as he played. However, virtually every musician will stress that notation should never be used during public performances.

University students may use notation, either given to them or jotted down themselves, to help memorize new material, but they will always have the music memorized before a performance. Even young children, who don't yet know how to improvise and therefore don't really need to be freed of notation for musical purposes, are urged to memorize songs before concerts, or at the very least, to write crib notes on a small piece of paper which they can hide behind their instruments so that no one knows. As a way of summarizing some of the implications of the notation of Thai music, I would like to touch upon a few of Judith Becker's points regarding the impact of notation in Java, and contrast these to the Thai situation. Most obviously, Becker explains that "notation is considered to be progressive and modern, and is highly valued if not always practiced;" clearly, the situation is different in Thailand, where serious musicians are apologetic about the use of notation, and even amateurs know that one "shouldn't" use notation.

Therefore, the authority of written: versions-which Becker found in Java-does not exist in Thailand. Notation is not to be trusted. More deeply, Becker argues that notation is partly behind an increasing uniformity of Javanese styles, in which regional differences become negated and in which students closely duplicated the music of their teachers. They don't know enough about classical music in rural Thailand to speak of its changing relationship to urban styles, but I do know that within the urban context uniformity is not valued (except, for some, in an effort to standardize tuning). Some stylistic homogenization may be occurring today, but they would argue that this is not due to the technology of notation but to social factors, especially the authority of certain prestigious and well-placed individuals such as the composer Luang Pradit at the government's Department of Fine Arts-and the mixing of eclectic personnel in modern performance and study contexts. Furthermore, in parts of the Thai repertoire, such as instrumental solos, students are supposed to duplicate exactly the versions of their teachers but then, that repertoire is too complex and too special to be notated anyway. Finally, Becker contrasts the traditional training of the Javanese musician, in which a student absorbs a musical totality, with the modern practice of receiving lessons of finite periods. Because of new, urban work schedules, a teacher cannot teach for long hours, and students may not be able to study as part of an ensemble but rather learn their instrument's part alone.

Notation is a convenient tool in such a setting. To Becker, this implies an experiential change on the part of musicians, who learn to perceive one instrumental line as standing "apart" from others. In Thailand, identical changes have occurred in teaching contexts, though-since notation is looked down upon-it is the tape recorder which today serves as convenient tool (here I'm disregarding the amateurs and young children who learn solely from notation). Students may record compositions during lessons, and then study with the tape between lessons. Practicing alone with a tape recording may alter the perception and experience of student musicians as Becker described-learning to view one line apart from an ensemble but the authority of the teacher rather than of an abstracted "version" remains, for it is the teacher on the tape. Authority is not transferred to an enduring technological record. To conclude, both indigenous and Western forms of musical notation are used by musicians in the Thai classical tradition, yet the two were adopted for different reasons and continue to function in different ways today. From the start, the Thai systems were intended to aid memory and speed the teaching of music, while Western notation has been used in efforts at preservation. It appears that as it is used by professional musicians and seriously committed students in Bangkok, notation changes neither the music nor the teacher disciple relationship in particularly significant ways. As it is used in the schools and by amateur musicians, notation brings music into new contexts. Yet amateurs who "receive" songs in written form still maintain certain fundamental features of traditional teacher- student relationships.

Catherine Bird's thesis "The Influence of the Javanese Gamelan on Selected Piano Works of Claude-Achille Debussy" (1982) analyzes the synthesis in the composer's post-1889 piano music, including *Ballade* (1890), *Nocturne* (1890), *Preludes Books 1 and 2* (1910, 1913), and "Pagodes" from *Estampes* (1903). Bird asserts that in achieving gamelan sonorities, Debussy applied pentatonic and whole-tone scales, which are roughly similar to the slendro tuning of the Javanese ensemble, as the underlying tonal basis for both melodic and harmonic elements. The composer also paraphrased a single "nuclear theme," creating the gamelan's distinctive ostinato characteristic, as opposed to developing different motifs or themes in the Western musical practice. To reproduce the gamelan's texture, Debussy employed heterorhythmic or "layered" textures and colotomic punctuation of the gamelan's largest gongs. Moreover, he imitated loud soft dynamics and avoided crescendo or diminuendo and adopted gamelan musical structure which lacks of Western musical concept of development. Besides the piano music, these gamelan features also appear in Debussy's orchestral works, particularly *La Mer* ("The Sea," 1903-05) at rehearsal numbers 5, 14, 54-55, and 62-63, where the composer incorporated the combination of various melodic, rhythmic, registral, timbral variants of a single linear movement to mirror the gamelan's sonorities and compositional techniques. With this new synthesis approach, Debussy created more alternatives for succeeding composers in experimenting with the fusion between Eastern and Western music.

In "The East in the West: Evocations of the Gamelan in Western Music," Mervyn Cooke provides an account of later compositions following Debussy's footsteps of evoking gamelan sonorities. Maurice Ravel (1875-1937) carefully selected a percussion ensemble to capture authentic gamelan sonorities in the orchestral version of "Laideronnette, impératrice des pagodes" from *Ma mere l'oye* (1908-10), while Béla Bartók (1881-1945) adopted a specific Balinese scale in "Island of Bali" from volume 4 of the *Mikrokosmos* (1940). On the other hand, Francis Poulenc (1899-1963) was retrogressive by merely borrowing from gamelan music without synthesizing it with Western musical concepts in *Concerto for Two Pianos and Orchestra* (1932) and the Prologue of the opera *Les mamelles de Tirésias* (1944).

Furthering Debussy's scrutiny of gamelan music and Bartók's fieldwork of Eastern European musical cultures starting in 1906, ethnomusicologists began their interest in hands-on experiences of non-Western musical traditions. Accuracy of the studied music in all musical aspects, whether melody, mode, rhythm, texture, formal structure, tuning system, and performance practice, became a crucial standpoint in aurally transcribing the original music into Western notation. Researchers also systematized non-musical aspects, such as aesthetics, philosophies, cultural contexts, languages, and religions, which later became as influential as musical sonorities. These phenomena affected composers in that they no longer added exotic colors to their music merely through simple imitation of non-Western musical elements.

Moreover, some composers even received firsthand experiences of non-Western musics from native masters. This approach offered the composers a new perception on the actual compositional process through authentic performance techniques and practices and through the point of view of musical insiders. Growing up near the Chinese and Japanese districts in San Francisco in the first decades of the twentieth century, Henry Cowell (1897-1965) experienced traditional and folk music of immigrants and later absorbed them into his compositions. His first Asian influenced composition appeared in 1917 in the piano piece "Amiable Conversation," which was modeled on the tone of Cantonese dialect.³⁹ In the 1920s and 1930s, Cowell developed relationships with outstanding performers of non-Western musics and studied native instruments with them. In 1931, he received a Guggenheim award to study comparative musicology with Erich von Hornbostel in Berlin, where he also encountered Hornbostel's collection of 22,000 cylinder recordings of music from all parts of the world. In his speech at the 1961 Tokyo conference "The East-West Music Encounter," Cowell claimed that he was the first Western composer to study several Eastern musical traditions from within and with Eastern teachers. Although Cowell did not consider himself an ethnomusicologist, he taught courses on the "Musical Systems of the World" and "Primitive and Folk Music of the World" with live performances at The New York's New School for Social Research, as well as wrote articles on exotic and world music subjects. He devoted himself to the Asian Society and became the first board chairman of the Society for Asian Music. His lectures and articles had a great impact on his colleagues and younger composers in exploring and combining non-Western musical elements in their compositions.

As these composers were searching for new musical languages, non-Western music became a means to explore new colors and techniques and to deviate their music from the norm. From the 1930s to the 1960s, Cowell traveled to Europe and Asia, experiencing a wide variety of musical and cultural practices. His preoccupation with non-Western music and world travels resulted in two methods of Cowell's transcultural composition: the first focused specifically on musical aspects of a particular culture and the second blended together various styles in less obviously pronounced ways. The first method appears in, for instance, Cowell's adoption of "sliding tones"—the tonal inflections influenced by Chinese speech and operatic singing into his compositions. Nancy Yunhwa Rao analyzes Cowell's theory of sliding tones and the way the composer applies the concept to acquire dramatic effect and expressive power in his compositions, for example, the opening movement of the prologue to *Atlantis* (1926)—ballet music for orchestra and voices, the song "Rest" (1933),

Symphony Nos. 11-15 (1954-1961), and the Trio in Nine Short Movements (1965). The second method, on the other hand, concerns the blending of Chinese, Japanese, or Indonesian musical references, appearing in, for example, String Quartet No. 4 "United Quartet" (1936), American Melting Pot (1940), and Variations for Orchestra (1956). Within either of these two transcultural musical methods, nonetheless, Cowell combined the non-Western musical elements with the ultramodern techniques that he practiced in his youth to create his distinctive synthesis, which Cowell himself perceived to be a much more sustainable and more "international" musical style.

Although Cowell might have been the first American composer to study Asian instruments with native musicians, it was actually his younger colleague Colin McPhee (1900- 1964) who pushed the "insider" approach to the extreme when he spent almost seven years in Bali, building not only a Balinese style house but also Balinese gamelans. During his time in Bali, McPhee conducted research on Balinese gamelan by organizing and recording techniques and repertoire of various Balinese gamelan groups, which were different from place to place due to the lack of standardization in instrument building, tuning, and notation systems. He spent several hours a day transcribing gamelan music from Balinese masters and published meticulous transcriptions in various forms for Western musical instruments, including the three well-known transcriptions for two pianos published under the title *Balinese Ceremonial Music* by G. Schirmer in 1940. These transcriptions are an extension of McPhee's research, conveying information about performance practice that is not present in the direct notations for traditional instruments such as how a melody must be doubled at the octave or how it is divided between two players of same instruments. In Bali, McPhee also established gamelan ensembles in order to revive older repertoire. These ensembles allowed him to receive the firsthand study of the music, especially for older styles, as well as the opportunity to observe Balinese pedagogical methods intimately. McPhee's musical fusion appeared as early as 1931 in *Octette*, which he included Balinese scales. However, it was not until the toccata for two pianos and orchestra *Tabuh-Tabuhan* (1936) that McPhee took a major step toward fusing the Eastern and Western sounds, borrowing not only from the gamelan but also from jazz and Latin American popular music.

He scored *Tabuh-Tabuhan* for a pseudo-gamelan, comprising two pianos, Western percussion instruments, and two Balinese gongs and placed these instruments against a standard symphony orchestra. Although the Western concept of fast-slow-fast movements influenced the work's structure, McPhee's compositional process for *Tabuh-Tabuhan* was similar to the process by which Balinese music is composed (or, to be accurate, "rearranged") by taking fragments from existing compositions and binding them into new works. Within each section of the three movements, McPhee drew most of the themes from his own gamelan transcription, either in direct quotations or transpositions of the transcriptions; other few themes are newly-created, yet they still capture the essence of different gamelan styles.

The central concept behind *Tabuh-Tabuhan* is the layering of individual lines, which were McPhee's apparent fusion of gamelan technique, formed by the stratification of intricate rhythmic patterns through the simultaneous use of distinct registers, pitch patterns, and ostinatos.⁵⁰ The harmonic materials, however, have both Western and Balinese characteristics. The Oriental harmony came from various forms of the Balinese pelog and slendro scales, which resulted in chords generated from four- and five-note scales.

Beside *Tabuh-Tabuhan*, Balinese references also appear in most of McPhee's later compositions: *Transitions* (1954) and *Nocturne* (1958) follow the Balinese manner of drawing upon pre-existent music, punctuating rhythmic structures with gong, and coloring with percussive effects; while *Symphony No. 2* ("Pastoral," 1957) and *Concerto for Wind Orchestra* (1960) add Balinese melodies to the Balinese compositional systems. Nevertheless, it was not the transcriptions or compositions but McPhee's writings on Balinese gamelan that became the composer's legacy. After McPhee settled back in New York City, he devoted himself to propagandizing Balinese music through articles in *Modern Music*, *Musical Quarterly*, *Musical America*, the *Peabody Bulletin*, and the *New York Times*. While his book *A House in Bali* (1946) details his daily life on the island, *A Club of Small Men* (1948) tells a delightful children's story about the gamelan *angklung* that he established for Balinese boys. Perhaps McPhee's most important writing was an encyclopedia titled *Music in Bali* (1966), which is the culmination of McPhee's almost thirty years of experience and observation of Balinese gamelan.⁵³ With abundant musical examples and illustrations, the book presents Balinese gamelan's relation to and position in its culture and thoroughly analyzes the structure and style of each type of the gamelans encountered by McPhee in the 1930s. Although McPhee devoted himself to gamelan music and made the first inroads for gamelan into the American consciousness, Lou Harrison (1917-2003) ultimately solidified gamelan's popularity in the United States.

For these efforts, Harrison rather than McPhee has been acknowledged as the "Father of Gamelan." In spite of that sobriquet, Harrison's interest was not limited to gamelan. Rather, Harrison was the United States' most prominent and determined advocate of a global approach to instruments and intonational systems, as he immersed himself deeply in the theories, practices, and instruments of various cultures (for example, ancient Greek, European, South American, Native American, or Asian) and composed not only for traditional Indonesian, Korean, and Chinese instruments and ensembles, but also for his replicas of those ensembles

constructed out of materials from the United States. Similar to Cowell, Harrison experienced many styles of Asian musics at San Francisco's Chinatown during his collegiate years. In the spring of 1935, he enrolled in Cowell's course "Music of the Peoples of the World" at the University of California, San Francisco. This course led to subsequent private composition lessons with Cowell, which resulted in Harrison's great passion for non-Western music. Through Cowell and his friend Dorothy James, Harrison heard recordings of Balinese compositions and other world musics before experiencing a live Balinese gamelan at the 1939 Golden Gate Exposition and later at San Francisco's Curran Theater. In April 1961, Harrison accepted an invitation to the "East-West Music Encounter Conference" in Tokyo.

Surprisingly, the conference allowed him to study firsthand Indonesian gamelan with two American experts: Colin McPhee for the Balinese style and Mantle Hood for the Javanese style. Harrison received more hands-on experiences of Asian instruments in 1962 when he traveled to Korea and Taiwan for intensive private study of traditional Korean and Chinese musics.⁵⁸ Upon his return to the United States, he enthusiastically lectured on Korean and Chinese musics and formed a small Chinese chamber group that presented hundreds of performances of the two nations' repertoires. He taught world music classes at several universities in California and was appointed composer-in-residence for the "Festival of Music and Art of this Century" of the East-West Center at University of Hawaii in the spring of 1963. However, the most significant of his contributions in the dissemination of world music in the United States took place in 1971 when he successfully constructed an "American Gamelan," which consists of a set of metallophones built from easy-to-find materials such as steel conduit tubing, aluminum slabs, and stacked tin cans as resonators. Regarding his cross-cultural compositions, Harrison varyingly combined Western and Eastern musical elements to compose for traditional Asian solo instruments, Asian ensembles, and mixed European-Asian ensembles.

For Asian solo instruments, he followed distinctive techniques and timbres of Asian instruments, but composed within the standard forms of Western music. For example, in *Psalter Sonata* (1961) for cheng, Harrison combined the binary form of Domenico Scarlatti's sonatas and the distinctive instrumental techniques of the cheng—ornamentations and pitch alterations following a single pluck, created by pressing on the strings to the left of the movable bridges with the fingers of the left hand.⁶⁰ He also fused ancient Western and Eastern tuning systems through the combination of justly tuned and pentatonic scales with an added #7. In *Wesak Sonata* (1964), Harrison fused standard cheng finger techniques with Western rhythmic concept of tempo shifts and many 3/8 phrases alternating with 2/8 or 2/4.

While Harrison remained more conventional in composing for traditional Asian ensembles, following Javanese forms and styles with some added Western compositional procedures, he experimented with various cross-cultural practices through his works for mixed East-West musical instruments, in which he added Western solo instruments to an Asian ensemble or vice versa.⁶³ His first attempt in this area was the *Concerto in Slendro* (1961), which relatively follows the gamelan's performance practices with some added harmony on the keyboards, a celesta and two tack-pianos, that are retuned to an Indonesian-inspired pentatonic mode. In *Concerto for Pipa and String Orchestra* (1997), however, the harmony, structure, and tutti sections lean more toward the Western side, yet the pipa's virtuosic techniques are evident in soloistic passages and its distinctive gliding tone is also imitated by the orchestra. The interest of gamelan continued throughout the twentieth century, especially in the United States. With the growth of ethnomusicology and recording companies, recordings of gamelan music increasingly disseminated throughout scholarly circles, causing many American universities to establish gamelan ensembles. Composers no longer necessarily received training from the masters abroad but analyzed gamelan transcriptions, listened to gamelan recordings, and studied in gamelan ensembles in the United States.

Unlike those early twentieth-century American composers who aimed to capture the sound, practice, and compositional procedure of traditional gamelan music, their younger colleagues merely evoked the gamelan through the use Western percussion instruments with some incorporated gamelan techniques and turned their focus on non-Western music more to the aesthetical and philosophical aspects, particularly those of the Chinese *I Ching*. With this interest emerged a new type of cross-cultural composition, synthesizing Asian aesthetics and philosophies with the mid-twentieth century Western musical styles. Harry Partch (1901-1974) delved into another level of cross-cultural composition by creating musical works possessing not only characteristics of non-Western music but also their aesthetic principles that are inhabited by both performers and audiences. Partch's Asian influences came directly from his parents who had been missionaries in China at the turn of the century and his encounters with Chinese music in San Francisco, particularly with Cantonese opera.

His interest in the Pythagorean concept from Hermann Helmholtz's *On the Sensations of Tone* (1923) and his awareness of different Asian tuning systems led him to various experiments in microtonalism and intonational systems, which resulted in his adaptation and invention of musical instrument design and construction, either from conventional instruments or new materials such as Pyrex carboys, light bulbs, and whisky bottles. Although Harry Partch relentlessly denied his quotation of any Asian musics, S. Andrew Granade proves in his article "Rekindling Ancient Values: The Influence of Chinese Music and Aesthetics on Harry Partch" that the composer adopted not only the Chinese tradition of poet/musicians into his Monophonic

system in his early years but also absorbed East Asian musical aesthetic principles into his conception of Corporeality later on in his life. The former—a system in which all intervals emerge from one fundamental pitch, while rhythm and melody originate in the spoken inflection of the text—is found in his Monophonic solo performances on the Adapted Viola and the Adapted Guitar. The later concept appears in his theatrical works, beginning with *King Oedipus: Music-Dance Drama* in 1951, synthesizing both visual and aural aspects with the intention to engage performers and audiences utterly on a bodily level.⁶⁹ While Partch reflected East Asian aesthetics through his musical fusion, John Cage (1912-92) absorbed East Asian philosophies and paired them into his compositions, visual art, and poetry.

Cage experienced Asian musics began in the 1930s through his studies with Henry Cowell (including the participation in Cowell's "Music of the World's Peoples" lectures in New York) and through his lifelong friendship with Lou Harrison. In the early 1940s, he learned about Asian philosophies and aesthetics when Harrison introduced him the Chinese I Ching. However, Cage gave little interest in the philosophy and still notably composed in the Western style until a decade later when he found the East Asian sources responsive and inspired him with the potential of compositional indeterminacy. He read a fair amount of South Asian aesthetics and East Asian philosophies and was re-introduced to the I Ching by his student Christian Wolff when he was completing *Concerto for Prepared Piano and Chamber Orchestra* in 1951. This time he found the I Ching concept correlated with the systematic procedures of the grids he created when composing the concerto's first two movements, a move he made in order to relinquish his subjective choices. In applying the I Ching, Cage ultimately abnegated the world of choice and successfully moved his composing into the world of chance.

Cage's studies of the I Ching resulted in striking transformations of his musical language in the early 1950s, especially with *Music of Changes* (1951) and *4'33"* (1952). Although the interpretation of Cage's notorious work *4'33"* is often associated with the "nothingness" philosophy of Zen Buddhism, the work can also be perceived through the lens of I Ching, whose basic principle is derived from yin and yang—two opposite yet complementary primal forces in nature which include all dualist opposites: silence, as opposed to sound, in this case. Whereas in *Music of Changes*, Cage employed the process of creating the sixty-four hexagrams of I Ching in the compositional process so that the sounds were unimpeded and interpenetrating. In the same way as a throw of three coins determines the I Ching hexagrams, Cage tossed coins three times to identify his particular hexagrams in order to regulate sonority, durations, and dynamics for the work before notating the results on staff paper. Cage later pushed the boundary of his I Ching approach by applying chance operations into more and more aspects of the music, for example, clefs, accidentals, and playing techniques in *Music for Piano* (1953); mode, tonic note, and the first note of each half measure in *Cheap Imitation for Piano* (1969); and the compositional method of the ninety pieces in *Song Books* (1970), deciding that each piece was to be composed by either using a method already employed in the *Song Books*, a variant of a previous method, or a whole new method. Although chance procedures freed Cage from decision making at the micro level, he still took control of the music at the macro level by creating the list of possibilities from which the I Ching randomly selected. This choice prevented the music from turning into complete chaos while allowing Cage to achieve his aesthetic goal of liberating the sound. Besides his interest in Chinese philosophy, gamelan music also attracted Cage's fascination, which might have formed its root from Cowell's lectures during Cage's early years. The sonorities and ostinato patterns of the gamelan ensemble are apparent in many of his prepared piano works such as *Bacchanale* (1940), *Amores* (1943), and *Sonatas and Interludes* (1946-48).

Moreover, a number of his works for percussion ensemble exhibit Cage's fondness for the gamelan sonority more clearly, especially in the stratified ostinato patterns and syncopations of *First Construction* (1939) and *Double Music* (1941). *Second Construction* (1940) assimilated the gamelan more closely with its glockenspiel melody alluding to Balinese scales. However, unlike Cowell, McPhee, or Harrison, Cage was inspired by gamelan sonorities to create new sounds in Western music. He rarely applied gamelan techniques such as stratified rhythms, heterophony, colotomic punctuation, and nuclear themes simultaneously throughout a whole composition as in original gamelan music; rather he divided his music into different sections and alternately used the techniques in each section, and combined them with his own experiments of other techniques and sound sources in order to get various tone colors. Cage's transformation of Asian aesthetics and philosophies became one of distinct influences on minimalism, a musical movement emerging in 1960s San Francisco and New York. In order to achieve the contemplative, time-suspending qualities of gamelan and other non-Western music, minimalism reacted against the goal-oriented directionality of Western music by replacing tension, release, and climax with repetitions and steady rhythm. Nevertheless, minimalism rejected Cage's chaotic sound resulting from chance operation, as well as the totally controlled and complicated atonal music of the total serialists—the opposite musical movement to Cage's chance music—and aimed to create more simple and accessible tonal music that occupied a middle ground. This new guise of Asian aesthetics and philosophies in Western tonal music became a significant framework to the entire minimalist output, including that of Steve Reich.

While other pioneering minimalists like La Monte Young (b.1935), Terry Riley (b.1935), and Philip Glass (b.1937) immersed themselves in Indian raga, Steve Reich (b.1936) focused on Balinese gamelan and

West African drumming. Reich began his interest in gamelan during the 1960s after reading McPhee's *Music in Bali* and listening to recordings of gamelan music. Over a decade later in the summers of 1973 and 1974 at the University of Washington in Seattle and the Center for World Music in Berkeley, respectively, Reich remembered the book and intensively studied gamelan's instruments and musical structures, which soon yielded its fruits in one of the minimalist landmarks, *Music for Eighteen Musicians* (1976). The work begins and ends with a cycle of eleven pulsating chords, each chord serving as the harmonic foundation of one section of the piece—one way to understand this structure is as Reich's adaptation of the colotomic structure, the rhythmic foundation of gamelan music. The similarities do not stop with rhythmic structure but extend to aesthetics as well. *Music for Eighteen Musicians* is performed from memory and without a conductor like a communal ritual in gamelan tradition, meaning that the metallophone provides cues for changes within and between sections in the same way as a drummer calls for changes of pattern in Balinese gamelan. The minimalist concept of rhythmic and textural clarity combined with hypnotic repetitiveness through ostinato (most of the time within stratified rhythm) has continued in the works of post-minimalist composers. These composers enriched the concept with their own expressive means and stylistic juxtapositions, resulting in an increasingly diverse musical style as seen in the works of numerous composers, including Daniel Lentz (b.1942), William Duckworth (1943-2012), John Adams (b.1947), Meredith Monk (b.1942), Michael Torke (b.1961), the "Bang on A Can" collective (Michael Gordon [b.1956], David Lang [b.1957], and Julia Wolfe [b.1958]), as well as in the later works of the minimalist pioneers themselves.⁷⁸ Similar to Cage and Reich, mid-century European composers cared less about capturing the authenticity of Balinese gamelan music than evoking its sonorities and aesthetic qualities although they still adopted some gamelan techniques such as polyphonic stratification, pentatonic emphasis, repetitive motivic structure, and colotomic gong punctuation. Both Benjamin Britten (1913-76) and Olivier Messiaen (1908-92) displayed gamelan sonorities within the confines of Western instruments, particularly through Western percussion instruments grouped in a pseudo-gamelan section in their orchestral works. Reflecting gamelan aesthetics, Britten often associated Balinese materials with a supernatural place or character in his operas and ballet, while Messiaen applied gamelan techniques of cyclical repetition to serve the timeless.

During the rise of post-minimalism in the 1980s, a group of so-called "new wave" composers emerged, made up primarily of Chinese composers who were born in the mid-1950s and sent to forced labor in the remote countryside to be "re-educated" by peasants during the Cultural Revolution (1966-76). After Mao Zedong's death, they pursued their study in leading Chinese music conservatories. In this academic setting, they participated in master classes and lectures of guest composers such as Chou Wen-chung, Alexander Goehr (b.1932), George Crumb (b.1929), Toru Takemitsu, and Isang Yun, who visited China through cultural exchange programs between China and Western countries. As part of their conservatory training, the young composition students also went to the countryside to collect folksongs during their summer vacations. After being exposed firsthand to Chinese traditional culture and music during the re-education and to Western modern music during their conservatory years, these new wave composers developed a new trend of Chinese music composition by abandoning the exhausted fusion of Chinese melody and Western diatonic harmony, and incorporating rhythms, timbres, textures, and aesthetics commonly found in Chinese music with Western avant-garde techniques to reflect the social, economic, and political changes of their time. In the mid-1980s and early 1990s, the new wave composers went abroad to further their education in European and North American continents before establishing themselves as composers-in-residence, artistic directors, conductors, guest lecturers, as well as professors at major universities, some in the United States and others in China.

Among their numbers were the internationally-known Chen Yi, Zhou Long, Bright Sheng, and Tan Dun.⁸⁰ These four composers came to the United States and received fellowships at Columbia University to study under the guidance of renowned professors, including the Chinese-born American composer Chou Wenchung, who has had a great influence on next generations of Asian (as well as American) composers, particularly on the subject of cross-cultural fusion. Chou Wen-chung is perhaps the first Chinese composer who attempted to synthesize Chinese musical elements with modern Western music.⁸¹ Born in China and raised in an extraordinarily intellectual family that placed equal value on Chinese traditions and the study of Western culture, Chou studied both violin and erhu (a two-stringed Chinese fiddle) in the multicultural Shanghai scene. Japanese occupation during World War II caused Chou to leave the country, and he arrived in the United States in 1946 on a five-year architecture scholarship at Yale University. With a strong desire to be a composer, he later became music major at the New England Conservatory where he took private compositional lessons with Nicolas Slonimsky (1894-1995) who urged him to develop his compositional style using both Chinese and Western materials.

Chou took the suggestion and began studying the sources and playing techniques of the Chinese qin (a seven-stringed zither) as well as Chinese aesthetics from poetry, painting, calligraphy, and Taoist philosophy. In this holistic search of Chinese arts, Chou was also drawn aesthetically to the Confucian ideal of *ya*, the high value placed on an individual's ability to cultivate several different subjects simultaneously.⁸³ The study of Chinese music, aesthetics, and philosophy resulted in Chou's first successful work, *Landscapes* (1949), which

employs Chinese pentatonic melodies and the aesthetic principle of *ya*, as do other Chou's works from his early period (pre-1952).

However, Chou did not merely subjugate Chinese melodies under a Western harmonic framework, but applied techniques of musical structure, voice leading, supporting sonorities, timbre, and emotion from the original Chinese melodies to his compositions for Western instruments. With these constructed melodies, together with contrasts in orchestral timbre, sparse orchestration, subtle dynamic changes, and the alternation between quartal consonance and dissonant dyads, Chou evoked the brushstrokes, lines, and spaces of Chinese calligraphy and painting as well as the expression of Chinese poetry. Through Colin McPhee, Chou met his next composition teacher, Edgard Varèse (1883- 1965), who became the most influential person in Chou's compositional development. Under Varèse's influence, Chou entered an experimental period (1952-1959) in which he merged the Chinese concept of a single tone's timbre—particularly in the music of the *qin*, whose timbre consists of at least twenty-six varieties—and the idea of controlled flow of ink from Chinese calligraphy with the Varèsean sound mass as reflected in *And the Fallen Petals* (1954) and *Soliloquy of a Bhiksuni* (1958).⁸⁵ The fusion emanated from various sonorities that were organically derived from a single tone or theme and the interplay between these layers of sonorities, creating a continuity of motion and tension in a spatial equilibrium.⁸⁶ Upon his graduation from Columbia University in 1954, the Rockefeller Foundation awarded Chou a grant to study classical Chinese music, philosophy, and drama intensively for two years.

The study culminated in Chou's development of a compositional system called "variable modes," constructed according to the principles of the I Ching that became the principal feature of his later works. Chou created his eight variable modes by translating the eight trigrams of the I Ching, and varied the modes' structure and presentation from piece to piece, for example, the modes of *Metaphors* (1960) derive from the replacement of yin as a trichord containing two whole steps and yang as a minor third.⁸⁷ As two Chinese trigrams are combined to create a hexagram, Chou combined two modes together to form a complete ascending and descending scale. He also applied the concept of inversion, retrograde, and retrograde inversion in creating different types of his modes. Chou applied this fundamental concept of variable modes to all of his post-1960 works, with the exceptions of *Yü Ko* (1965) and *Beijing in the Mist* (1986), but varied the transformational procedure to create different musical contents, formal layouts, and structural organizations for each composition. However, all of these works carry one similarity in that they do not necessarily evidence an Oriental sound, but present Chinese references in the compositional process through their embrace of Chinese aesthetic and I Ching philosophy.

Chou's compositional methods and techniques had a great impact on his students' works, especially those of the new wave composers, with the most apparent influence remained in the aspect of cross-cultural composition or "confluence," in Chou's term, which he described as "a new mainstream that will integrate all musical concepts and practices [of different traditions] into a vast expanse of musical currents. But each individual culture will preserve its own uniqueness, its own poetry."⁸⁸ Similar to Chou Wen-chung's compositions, the works of the younger Chinese composers reflect confluence through Asian aesthetics and philosophies. Yet, unlike Chou who was interested in Chinese classical arts, these composers gravitated toward the folk music they encountered in their youth, particularly during the Cultural Revolution (not only their melodies, but also rhythms, timbres, textures, structure, and socio-cultural context). Moreover, while Chou's fusion approach is arduous, objective, and rational, new wave composers aimed primarily to evoke emotions. As a result, their compositions reflect Chinese sonorities much more than their mentor's even though they merged Chinese elements with the twelve-tone method, free atonality, as well as other avant-garde musical techniques just like their teacher did. The Chinese flavor is probably most obvious in the works of Bright Sheng, Chou's first student among the four presented here.

Bright Sheng grew up in an intellectual, artistic family. His father was a radiologist who also played a *jing hu*, two-stringed fiddle in a Peking opera while his mother was an engineer who played the piano and taught the instrument to Sheng from the age of four. During the Cultural Revolution, Sheng became a percussionist and arranger for an art troupe in Xining, a remote region in the Qinghai province of the northwestern China, where he studied and collected local folk music. Sheng entered Shanghai Conservatory of Music in 1978 and learned both Western and Chinese traditional music. In 1980, he immigrated to the United States and two years later pursued his master's at Queens College of the City University of New York, studying under George Perle and Hugo Weisgall before beginning his doctorate at Columbia University in 1984. Bright Sheng's works are distinctive for their lyrical melodies, which are derived from folksongs, especially *hua'er*, a type of folksong popular in the Qinghai region.

His treatment of these folksongs is congruent with the original practice, which focuses on linear lines. Sheng either quoted folksongs or fragments of the songs or applied pitch class sets derived from folk tunes as the main motifs and built up these fragments or sets through techniques of motivic development, twelve-tone processes, or counterpoint. In addition, Sheng blended Eastern and Western music together by modulating these melodic lines according to the Chinese music theory, while treating the harmonic elements with Western techniques of polytonality through the simultaneous use of several Chinese pentatonic modes.⁸⁹ Not only

melodies but also rhythms, vocal singing, and instrumental styles of Chinese music motivated Sheng's fusion. *Tibetan Swing* (2002) illustrates how Sheng assimilated the dance rhythms of Tibetan long sleeves swing and foot stomp steps.⁹⁰ The vocal part of *Three Chinese Love Songs* blends Peking opera's vocal style into Western singing by adding portamenti and glissandi, especially an upward glissando with an abrupt release at the end of a phrase.

Similarly, Western string instruments also assimilate the portamenti, glissandi, grace notes, and microtones of Chinese strings' performance practices, as heard in *Seven Tunes Heard in China* (1995) in which the solo cello plays in an erhu-like manner. Apart from Chinese musical sonorities, Sheng also found an inspiration from Chinese extra-musical elements as seen in his two most well-known symphonic works: *H'un (Lacerations): In Memoriam 1966-1976* (1988) and *Nanking! Nanking!* (1999). *H'un* evokes the terror of the Cultural Revolution mainly through its atonal sonic images and some additional rhythmic figures of Chinese percussion, while *Nanking! Nanking!* depicts the notorious Nanking Massacre with the pipa telling the bloody story as the victim, witness, and survivor.⁹¹ These Chinese illustrations are even more discernable in the works of Sheng's colleague, Tan Dun, whose eclectic cross-cultural compositions represent not only musical concepts and practices of different Asian traditions but also symbolize folk and ancient rituals visually through dramatic theatrical elements. While the rest of the new wave presented here grew up in intellectual families, surrounded with Western classical music, Tan Dun was raised in a small countryside of Changsha, the capital of Southern Hunan province, where he experienced only folk music and dances, and taught h

Summary

Narong Prangcharoen pushed the limits of cross-cultural procedures used by Thai composers as well as those used by Western composers in his orchestral music by fusing Thai components with Western composing principles. While Thais often kept their Western musical techniques to those of the Classic and Romantic eras (with occasional flourishes from the mid-twentieth century), Westerners limited their cultural and musical allusions to China, Japan, Korea, and Indonesia. Prangcharoen embraces avenues not previously traveled by Thai and Western composers to develop his personal cross-cultural method, which has broadened repertoires with more conceivable composing strategies and sonorities. To bring this theory to a close, it is vital to compare Prangcharoen's fusion processes with those of other Thai and Western composers in order to adequately situate Prangcharoen in his historical context.

When Prangcharoen's fusion is juxtaposed with the five key practices of Thai crosscultural music history, traces of each technique are obvious, albeit Prangcharoen changes them to fit his writing style by relying more on contemporary compositional methods and treating Thai components with greater freedom. The fusion of Western music with Thai lyrics that arose in Thai religious music (Catholic chants from the sixteenth century and Christian hymns from the nineteenth century) and modern Thai popular music is a totally different process from Prangcharoen's symphonic fusion approach. With the exception of his solitary choral piece, *Echo of the Mountains* (2009), Prangcharoen never adds Thai words to any of his compositions, which widened this fusion by integrating Asian languages: Thai, Korean, Japanese, Malaysian, Indonesian, and Chinese.

The "Thai-ization" of early military band repertoire, which first emerged in the late nineteenth century, depicts Western military bands performing Thai music compositions in Thai style, properly integrating Thai methods of melody, rhythmic structure, and polyphonic layering. Prangcharoen's cross-cultural technique differs from this second fusion method in that he never completely adheres to any Thai musical customs, instead adopting all Thai musical aspects and conforming them to his writing style. In the early twentieth century, Prince Paribatra, who systematized the "Thaiized" process, also investigated the fusion process of eighteenth- and nineteenth-century Western musical exoticism in Thai military music by applying a Thai or pentatonic melody and resting it above Western-style harmonization. Prangcharoen promotes this exotic/pentatonic process; he never harmonizes it with Western traditional harmonic progressions, but often approaches pentatonic songs with motive development, polyphonic composition, and atonality techniques.

Prasidh Silapabanleng's *Siang Tian* (1970s and 1988) was the first to use the cross-cultural approach of combining Thai musical structure and performance techniques in a Western-style work. This procedure was extended significantly by American-Thai Bruce Gaston, who meticulously examined Thai musical customs while fusing them with avant-garde techniques. This Thai structural technique was conceptualized in the works of Gaston's pupil Jiradej Setabundhu, who literally converted the hierarchical pitch structure and centonization of Thai music to his devised language-based system, on which he built his Western-guise compositions. Although Prangcharoen uses the Thai thao's slow-medium-fast structure, as well as Thai instrumental and vocal performance traditions, he never confines himself to the Thai original's strict setting, but rather applies its principles in a wide meaning.

Thai extra-musical components were evident in the cross-cultural practice of Rear Admiral M.L. Usni Pramoj's and Somtow Sucharitkul's late-twentieth-century neo-Classic and neo-Romantic compositions. Prangcharoen follows this method but expands on it by fusing Thai storytelling with modern musical languages from the twentieth and twenty-first centuries. Among all Thai composers, Prangcharoen's cross-cultural method is most closely similar to that of his first composition master, Narongrit Dhamabutra, who incorporates practically all Thai and Western fusion techniques in his pieces. Nonetheless, despite the incorporation of twentieth-century timbres, Dhamabutra's musical vocabulary remains primarily neoRomantic. Prangcharoen's orchestral pieces, on the other hand, demonstrate a more sophisticated writing style that combines Thai musical themes with more contemporary creative strategies. Prangcharoen's fusion, which shifts focus from the East to the West, highlights characteristics from cross-cultural processes that have arisen in Western music history. When contrasted to the components pulled from Asian sources, it is clear that Prangcharoen's fusion differs from those of Western composers due to the integration of Thai resources. Since the late seventeenth century, Chinese allusions in opera have piqued the interest of Europeans, starting with Henry Purcell's *The Fairy Queen* (1692), followed by Italian drama per musica and comedic operas of the eighteenth century. This first merger of the Far East and the West in Western music history reflects the Chinese influence solely via non-musical features such as locations, costumes, storyline, characters, and language; the accompanying music, on the other hand, stays in typical Baroque and Classical form. Prangcharoen's fusion is comparable to this one in that he uses Thai extra-musical elements in his symphonic music without making any reference to Thai sonorities. However, unlike European composers, Prangcharoen does not refer to the East to escape from everyday life; on the contrary, Thai extra-musical references are an important part of his personality, and through them he expresses his feelings toward elements that make up his life as a Thai living and working in the West.

The fusion of pentatonicism in nineteenth-century Western music is analogous to the Thai exotic/pentatonic synthesis described above, in which an existing Eastern song or a freshly produced pentatonic melody sits above Western-style harmonization. Although Prangcharoen's cross-cultural process is occasionally akin to this fusion in terms of evoking Orientalist taste, Prangcharoen's technique does not limit itself to Western conventional harmonic progressions but also contains extended harmonics and atonality.

When Claude Debussy incorporated gamelan elements into his post-1889 pieces, a more "unique" synthesis evolved in Western music literature. Debussy strived for a more specific portrayal of gamelan sonority by incorporating characteristics of the original music, such as pentatonic and whole tone scales, an ostinato nuclear theme, heterorhythmic, and colotomic punctuation, into his timbrally-based melody, harmony, and atmosphere. Prangcharoen's and Debussy's synthesis are comparable in that they are audible transformations of the artists' impressions of traditional music without any effort to correctly integrate the original musical parts.

As a result, Prangcharoen's synthesis differs significantly from that of early twentieth-century American composers such as Henry Cowell, Colin McPhee, and Lou Harrison, who wrote from a "insider's" perspective. These American composers, like Bruce Gaston, researched traditional musics with zeal and strove to replicate archetypal musics in their works. Prangcharoen, on the other hand, never took official Thai music instruction and never expressed a desire to produce traditional musical works.

While early twentieth-century American composers strived for realistic Asian music techniques, mid-century American composers focused on East Asian aesthetics and ideologies for cross-cultural synthesis. While Harry Partch was enamored with East Asian musical aesthetic concepts and incorporated them into his Monophonic system and Corporeality, John Cage discovered a link between the Chinese I Ching and his notion of chance music. The introspective, time-delaying features of gamelan and other non-Western musics also established the groundwork for the whole minimalist output. Prangcharoen's synthesis of Thai aesthetics and philosophy is similar to that of these American composers in that neither adhered to the genuine meanings of those aesthetics and philosophies, but instead interpreted them and merged them with various Western composing approaches.

Conclusions

Prangcharoen's fusion is most closely tied to current Asian-American composers, particularly Chen Yi, Zhou Long, Bright Sheng, and Tan Dun's "new wave" group. These composers represent Chinese sonorities from traditional and folk music, fusing Chinese themes with the twelve-tone system, atonality, and other avant-garde music approaches while maintaining strong tonal centers. These new wave composers also use extra-musical Chinese allusions, such as Chinese history, Buddhism, literature, aesthetics, and ideologies. Prangcharoen, like many of these composers' pupils, follows in the footsteps of these Asian-American composers while expanding the resources for Asian allusions to incorporate Thai aspects as well.

After studying cross-cultural processes in Western and Thai classical music history, it is clear that Prangcharoen did not invent his musical fusion from scratch but rather incorporated influences from all existing syntheses and shaped them in his compositional style to establish his distinct fusion practice and musical language. His cross-cultural fusion of Thai and Western elements in the form of Western art music has added new perspectives to the familiar musical exotic repertoires and the new trend of Asian-American compositions

in Western music history, as well as to the conservative fusion that is still found in Thailand. Prangcharoen fills a hole in musical exoticism practice and tightens the relationship between Thai traditional and folk music and Western modern music through a powerful fusion, joining new ripples of musical influences spreading around the world in the same way that this thesis narrows the gap in musical scholarship on cross-cultural composition through the study of Prangcharoen's fusion practice.

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